

EFFECTS OF FREEZE-THAW CYCLES ON THE MECHANICAL AND THERMOMECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF GFRP LAMINATES PRODUCED BY VACUUM INFUSION

Tarikul Hasan, CERIS, IST, University of Lisbon, Bangladesh, tarikul.hasan@tecnico.ulisboa.pt
João R. Correia, CERIS, IST, University of Lisbon, Portugal, joao.ramoal.correia@tecnico.ulisboa.pt
Mário Garrido, CERIS, IST, University of Lisbon, Portugal, mario.garrido@tecnico.ulisboa.pt
Susana Cabral-Fonseca, Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil, Portugal, sbravo@lnec.pt
Francisco Soares, IST, University of Lisbon, Portugal, francisco.soares@tecnico.ulisboa.pt
Marco Jorge, ISEC, ARISE, Universidade do Minho, Portugal, marco@civil.uminho.pt
José Sena-Cruz, ISEC, ARISE, Universidade do Minho, Portugal, jsena@civil.uminho.pt

ABSTRACT

This paper presents an ongoing study about the effects of freeze-thaw cycles (FTC) on the thermomechanical and mechanical properties of GFRP composite laminates produced by vacuum infusion using two different resins, unsaturated polyester (UP) and vinyl ester (VE). So far, the laminates were subjected to 100 and 200 FTC, from -20 °C to 23 °C. After each ageing period, the degradation was assessed by dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) and different mechanical tests (tension, compression, flexure, in-plane shear and interlaminar shear). The results obtained so far indicate (i) slight-to-moderate reduction of the glass transition temperature, (ii) and also a decrease of the mechanical properties, especially in the flexural strength (up to 29%) and the compressive strength (up to 12%), which was partially reversible upon drying; and (iii) better overall performance of the VE composite.

KEYWORDS

Vacuum Infusion; Freeze-Thaw Cycles; Thermomechanical and Mechanical Properties; Durability.

INTRODUCTION

In the last three decades, fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP) composites have gained increased acceptance in civil engineering structural applications due to the various advantages they offer when compared to traditional materials, namely lightness, high specific strength and modulus, non-corrodibility, and low maintenance during service life.

In what concerns durability, FRP composites already have a long track record of use in various industries where they often face harsh environmental conditions (e.g. petrochemical industry, water and wastewater plants). While they generally exhibit good durability performance compared to traditional materials (Karbhari *et al.* 2003), FRP composites can experience degradation when exposed to various environmental agents, including moisture and chemicals, UV radiation and thermal effects, the latter encompassing thermal and freeze-thaw cycles.

Freeze-thaw cycles (FTC), which involve the combination of temperature and moisture, may cause significant effects on FRP composites. The following degradation mechanisms, reviewed in detail in Pritchard (1998) and Kharbari (2007), may be relevant: (i) the expansion and contraction associated to thermal cycles can affect the fibre-matrix bond, due to the mismatch in the coefficients of thermal expansion of reinforcing fibres and polymer matrices (e.g. 5×10^{-6} /K for E-glass and $30-200 \times 10^{-6}$ /K and $30-50 \times 10^{-6}$ /K for polyester and vinylester resins, CEN/TS 19101: 2022); (ii) the exposure to sub-zero temperatures causes hardening of the resin matrix, which may lead to microcracking and degradation of the fibre-matrix bond; (iii) the diffusion of (liquid) water involves various irreversible (hydrolysis) and reversible (plasticization, swelling) degradation mechanisms in the polymer resin,

and liquid water can also cause damage by capillarity at the fibre-matrix interface and in the fibres (pitting); (iv) the freezing of entrapped water may cause further degradation, due to volumetric changes, also creating additional pathways for water ingress. Altogether, these mechanisms can result in significant changes in thermo-physical and mechanical properties of FRP composites.

As for other environmental agents, the specific effects of freeze-thaw cycles on FRP composites depend on the constituent materials (fibre type and architecture, type of resin, additives and fillers), manufacturing process, and environmental conditions (temperature range, number of cycles, immersion medium). Most previous studies in this field refer to FRP laminates produced by pultrusion (e.g., Dutta and Hui 1996, Aniskevich *et al.* 2012, Grammatikos *et al.* 2016), hand layup (e.g., Zhang *et al.* 2001, Rivera and Karbhari 2002, Di Ludovico *et al.* 2012) or unspecified methods (e.g., Wu *et al.* 2006). On the other hand, very little information is available about the freeze-thaw performance of FRP composites produced by vacuum infusion, although there are applications in bridge decks (Osei-Antwi *et al.* 2013) and roofs (Keller *et al.* 2008).

In this context, this paper presents the results of an ongoing experimental study about the effects of exposure to freeze-thaw cycles on the thermomechanical and mechanical properties of relatively thick (6.5 mm) glass-FRP (GFRP) composites produced by vacuum infusion for civil engineering structural applications. Composites produced with unsaturated polyester (UP) and vinyl ester (VE) resins were preconditioned in water and, after exposure to different freeze-thaw cycles, the degradation of their thermomechanical and mechanical properties was evaluated through Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA), and different mechanical tests.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAMME

Materials

The specimens used in the experimental programme consisted of GFRP laminates, with dimensions of 700 mm × 250 mm and 6.5 mm of thickness. The laminates were manufactured by vacuum infusion (Figures 1 and 2), by Trimarine Compósitos. The GFRP laminates comprise E-glass fibre reinforcement (~57% fibre volume ratio) and two different resin types: unsaturated polyester (UP) and vinyl ester (VE). The fibre architecture of both composites was identical (enabling the direct comparison of the resin systems), comprising eight layers of unidirectional (0°, 625 g/m²), four quadriaxial (0°/+45°/90°/-45°, 835 g/m²) fabrics, and two outer layers of chopped strand mat (CSM, 300 g/m²). Following production, both types of composites underwent post-curing at 80 °C for a period of 12 hours.

Figure 1: Manufacturing of GFRP laminates by vacuum infusion.

Figure 2: GFRP-UP (left) and GFRP-VE (right) laminates.

The GFRP laminate with unsaturated polyester (GFRP-UP) was produced using PolyLite 720-691 resin (50-54% isophthalic polyester and 46-50% styrene); this resin mixture included 1.5% (wt%) methyl ethyl ketone peroxide-MEKP (Ketanox B180). The GFRP laminate with vinyl ester resin (GFRP-VE) was manufactured using Derakane 411 200 resin (52% epoxy vinyl ester resin and 48%

styrene); this resin mixture included 1.5% (wt%) methyl ethyl ketone peroxide-MEKP (Ketanox B180), 0.025% (wt%) dimethylaniline-DMA, 0.3% (wt%) cobalt octoate (1% cobalt), and 0.025% (wt%) 2,4-pentanedione.

Ageing protocol

The freeze-thaw cycles were carried out following the guidelines outlined in ASTM D7792/D7792M-15. The laminates underwent an initial conditioning period of water immersion at 20 °C for a period of 30 days. Subsequently, they were subjected to 100 and 200 freeze-thaw cycles (the laminates will also be subjected to 300 cycles) in a controlled environmental chamber, from *Aralab*, model ‘*FITOCLIMA 500 EPC45*’ (Figure 3). Each cycle consisted of an 8-hour wet stage, during which the laminates were immersed in water at 23 °C, followed by a 3.4-hour dry stage at -20 °C (with relative humidity of 50%), with a 2-hour heating/cooling period; the complete duration of each cycle was thus 13.4 hours (Figure 4). Upon completion of the cycles, the laminates were cut into specimens with various sizes, according to the geometry specified in each respective test standard for material characterization (test methods are described ahead). A group of specimens were then stored for a short period in water at 23 °C until the time of testing – *i.e.*, they were tested in wet state; another group of specimens were left to dry at room temperature for a period of 60 days before being tested, *i.e.*, they were tested in dry state.

Figure 3: GFRP laminate inside freeze-thaw chamber.

Figure 4: Temperature variation in material (T_m) and air (T_{air}) during a freeze-thaw cycle.

Test methods

Overview

The test methods included mass uptake measurements, carried out during the pre-conditioning period, and tests to measure the thermomechanical and mechanical properties of the GFRP laminates; these tests were carried out at three different stages: (i) before ageing, (ii) after pre-conditioning (30 days of water immersion at 23 °C); and (iii) after the freeze-thaw cycles. At these three stages, the following different tests were conducted: DMA tests, and tensile, compressive, in-plane shear, interlaminar shear and flexural tests (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Mechanical tests (from the left to the right): tensile, compressive, in-plane shear, interlaminar shear and flexural.

Mass uptake measurements

Mass uptake measurements were carried out according to some of the recommendations provided in ASTM D5229/D5229-20 and ISO 62:1999. Square specimens with 60 mm of side length (and 6.5 mm of thickness) were used in these tests and their lateral edges were coated with an epoxy resin (*Icosit K-101 N* from *Sika*) to guarantee uni-directional (through-thickness) moisture diffusion. For each type of resin, three replicate composite specimens were used. Before being immersed in distilled water, the specimens were dried to constant mass (± 1 mg) in a muffle at 40 °C. All mass measurements were done in an analytical balance with 0.1 mg accuracy.

Thermomechanical tests

The DMA tests were carried out using a dynamic mechanical analyser, model *Q800 DMA (TA Instruments)*, following the recommendations of parts 1 and 5 of ISO 6721:2019. A specimen size of 60 mm \times 10 mm \times 4 mm was adopted, heated from 25 °C to 200 °C at a rate of 2 °C/min, while being sinusoidally loaded in a dual cantilever type clamp system, at a constant frequency of 1 Hz and a strain amplitude of 15 μ m. Specimens used in these tests were prepared in a CNC milling machine, reducing the laminate thickness from 6.5 mm to 4 mm by milling on one of their surfaces (thus, the test specimens had non-symmetrical fibre layout). The glass transition temperature, T_g , was determined from the onset of decay of the storage modulus (E') curve, considering the average of two replicates.

Mechanical tests

The tensile tests were done using an Instron 5989 (with capacity of 600 kN) universal testing machine (UTM), following the recommendations of ISO 527-4:2021, using rectangular specimens of 300 mm \times 25 mm. The tests were done at a constant displacement rate of 2 mm/min, and the resulting strains were measured with a video extensometer (a 10-bit Sony CCD XCLU100 camera with a Fujinon F35SA-1, 35 mm f 1.4-22 lens, with an accuracy of $\pm 0.5\%$).

The compressive tests were done using the same Instron 5989 UTM and followed ISO 14126:1999. Rectangular specimens of 153 mm \times 25 mm were loaded at a constant displacement rate of 1.3 mm/min. The strains were also measured using a video extensometer.

The flexural tests were done in three-point bending, using the same Instron 5982 UTM, following ISO 14125:1998. Rectangular specimens of 195 mm \times 15 mm were loaded along a 130 mm span at a constant displacement rate of 5 mm/min.

The in-plane shear tests were done using an Instron 5982 (capacity of 100 kN) UTM, following the recommendations of ASTM D5379/D5379M-19 (Iosipescu/V-notch test method). Specimens of 76 mm \times 19 mm with V-shaped notches at their mid-section were loaded in shear at a constant displacement rate of 2 mm/min, and the resulting distortions were measured using a video extensometer.

The interlaminar shear tests were also done using the Instron 5982 UTM, following the recommendations of ISO 14130:1997. Rectangular specimens of 65 mm \times 32.5 mm were loaded in three-point bending along a span of 32.5 mm at a constant displacement rate of 1 mm/min.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mass uptake during pre-conditioning

Figure 6 presents the mass uptake of the two types of GFRP laminates, comprising unsaturated polyester (UP) and vinyl ester (VE) resins, during the 30-day pre-conditioning of water immersion at 20 °C. The results obtained prompt the following comments: in both laminates (i) the evolution of mass uptake with the square root of time followed the typical linear development of polymeric materials; (ii) the water absorption was slightly higher in the UP laminate, with maximum values of 0.27% and 0.25%, respectively, in GFRP-UP and GFRP-VE laminates; (iii) at the end of the pre-conditioning period, saturation was not achieved.

Figure 6: Mass uptake during pre-conditioning.

Thermo-mechanical behaviour

DMA analysis allows evaluating the viscoelastic behaviour of materials and determining their T_g ; in particular, DMA provides information about the mechanical behaviour of the material when subjected to sinusoidal loading under different temperatures and frequency conditions.

The experimental curves of the storage modulus (E') and $\tan \delta$ curves obtained for the two composite materials are presented in Figures 7 and 8 for the UP and VE laminates, respectively, for unaged specimens and for specimens subjected to 200 freeze-thaw cycles. Overall, regardless of the type of composite laminate and of the exposure to freeze-thaw cycles, the E' curves presented a sigmoidal shape, typical of polymeric materials: below T_g , E' is typically high, indicating a rigid or glassy state, and as the temperature approaches and exceeds T_g , E' decreases, indicating a transition to a rubbery state. The $\tan \delta$ curves also present the typical shape of polymeric materials, with a well-defined peak at elevated temperature due to glass transition. The DMA curves show no signs of secondary relaxations.

Figure 7: DMA curves for the GFRP-UP laminate.

Figure 8: DMA curves for the GFRP-VE laminate.

Figures 9 and 10 show the effect of 100 and 200 freeze-thaw cycles on the T_g (estimated from the onset of E') for the GFRP-UP and GFRP-VE laminates, respectively, tested in wet and dry conditions.

Both laminates present a decrease of T_g after exposure to freeze-thaw cycles, more pronounced for the UP laminate, with a maximum T_g reduction of 10 °C (from 86 °C in unaged condition) after 200 cycles, when tested in wet condition. This figure compares with a maximum reduction of 7 °C (from 95 °C in unaged condition) in the VE laminate.

Figure 9: Changes in T_g after freeze-thaw cycles, in wet and dry conditions, for the GFRP-UP laminate (error bars refer to minimum and maximum values).

Figure 10: Changes in T_g after freeze-thaw cycles, in wet and dry conditions, for the GFRP-VE laminate (error bars refer to minimum and maximum values).

As expected, for both materials, the changes observed in T_g when the materials were tested in dry condition are less significant than in wet condition, due to the plasticization effect caused by water on T_g . It is also observed that the UP laminate was more sensitive to this (reversible) plasticization phenomenon than the VE laminate, which was an expected result, considering the slightly different affinities that were exhibited by the two polymeric matrices in relation to water (Helbing and Karbhari 2007).

Mechanical behaviour

The tensile strength retention of both composites in the wet and dry states is presented in Figures 11 (UP) and 12 (VE); in these figures, as well as in the following ones, the error bars correspond to one standard deviation. Both composites showed low degradation in their tensile strength due to the freeze-thaw ageing protocol, with the UP composite showing the highest degradation levels of -5% after preconditioning (water immersion for 30 days) and -11% after 200 FTC. For the VE composite, the fluctuations in this property are within the experimental scatter, having little statistical relevance. For both composites, slight (up to ~5%) differences were found between wet and dry states, with dry specimens showing higher property retention, indicating the partial reversibility of degradation attributable to plasticization of the polymeric matrix.

Figure 11: Tensile strength retention for the UP composite.

Figure 12: Tensile strength retention for the VE composite.

In terms of compressive strength (Figures 13 and 14), both materials were more affected by the ageing protocol compared to tensile strength, especially the VE composite, which showed reductions of 9% after preconditioning and 15% after 200 FTC. Again, clear differences between wet and dry states

were observed for both composite materials, which were particularly expressive for the UP composite where after 200 FTC a 19% difference in average compressive strength retention was obtained between the two series (wet vs. dry). The compressive strength results generally presented significant scattering, a typical issue due to this property's relatively high susceptibility to local geometric imperfections and material defects (Sun *et al.* 2015). Compared to tensile strength, the lower compressive strength retention exhibited by both composites should be attributed to the higher matrix-dependence of this mechanical property.

Figure 13: Compressive strength retention for the UP composite.

Figure 14: Compressive strength retention for the VE composite.

Figure 15 plots the flexural strength retention of the UP composite and Figure 16 plots the same property for the VE composite. It is worth referring that failure was initiated in the upper laminae in compression, which governed the flexural strength of both composites; this was then followed by the rupture of the lower laminae in tension. The flexural strength of the UP composite was significantly more affected by the ageing protocol than the other properties of the same material. After preconditioning, the average flexural strength retention of the UP composite dropped by 17% and continued to decrease with FTC reaching a minimum retention of 71% after 200 cycles. However, most of this degradation was recovered upon drying (retentions of ~90%), suggesting that reversible degradation mechanisms, such as plasticization of the matrix (whose effects were also clear in terms of compressive strength), were responsible for most of the flexural strength reduction of the UP composite. The VE composite, on the other hand, exhibited relatively mild variations of flexural strength, showing the highest reductions (12%) after preconditioning, but later showing slight recovery during FTC; these figures are indicative of significantly lower impact of FTC in the VE composite compared to the UP composite in terms of flexural strength.

Figure 15: Flexural strength retention for the UP composite.

Figure 16: Flexural strength retention for the VE composite

Regarding in-plane shear strength, the retention of this property is shown in Figures 17 and 18, for UP and VE composites, respectively. For both materials, property increase was observed throughout the ageing protocol; only the VE composite exhibited some reductions after 200 FTC, which in fact resulted only in the reversion of the previous property increase (for wet conditions). These in-plane shear strength increases were 5% in wet state and up to 14% in dry state. The magnitude of these variations is mostly within the experimental scatter, so while probably being indicative of resin post-curing, they may also be associated with variability in material properties. Regardless of the reason(s) for such variations, no measurable degradation was found in the in-plane shear strength of both composites. This result is not particularly surprising given the good balance of fibre reinforcement along the 0/90/45-degree directions of the composites considered here, for which the in-plane shear strength becomes a more “fibre-dominated” property, being less sensitive to changes in the matrix properties. However, this particularly good performance suggests that fibre-matrix adhesion was not significantly affected by the ageing protocol (as otherwise the effectiveness of the multiaxial reinforcement should be affected likewise). Again, the differences between wet and dry state results suggest that plasticization is one of the main degradation mechanisms occurring in the resin matrices, in this case apparently more pronounced in the VE composite.

Figure 17: In-plane (IP) shear strength retention for the UP composite.

Figure 18: In-plane (IP) shear strength retention for the VE composite.

The interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) retention of UP and VE composites is presented in Figures 19 and 20, respectively. The changes in ILSS were very similar to those exhibited by the in-plane shear strength, with property increases of up to 10% in both materials. However, the differences between wet and dry states were less meaningful in the ILSS retention results, typically being well within the experimental scatter. These results are again indicative of good fibre-matrix adhesion – note that ILSS is strongly dependent on the adhesion at the interfaces between laminae, being also influenced by fibre bridging mechanisms.

Figure 19: Interlaminar shear strength retention for the UP composite.

Figure 20: Interlaminar shear strength retention for the VE composite.

Overall, a slight decreasing trend of ILSS between 100 and 200 FTC was observed both in this property (for all series) as well as in in-plane shear strength (except for the UP composite tested in dry state); the additional results that will be collected for 300 FTC may shed some light on whether this trend will continue (and thus indicate further degradation of these interfaces over time/cycles) or if it is only the result of material variability or experimental scatter.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

This paper presented results of an ongoing experiment that examined how freeze-thaw cycles (FTC) influence the thermomechanical behaviour and the mechanical properties of GFRP composite laminates produced by vacuum infusion. The 6.5 mm thick laminates investigated in this study comprise a multi-axial fibre architecture and two distinct resin systems, unsaturated (isophthalic) polyester and vinyl ester.

The exposure to 200 FTC (from -20 °C to 23 °C), which was preceded by 30 days of water immersion at 20 °C, had a slight-to-moderate influence on the T_g of both composite materials, which presented maximum reductions of 10 °C (from 86 °C in unaged condition) and 7 °C (from 95 °C in unaged condition) for the UP and VE composite laminates, respectively; in DMA tests, the UP laminate revealed higher sensitivity to water-induced plasticization, which results from the known higher affinity with water of unsaturated polyester compared to vinyl ester.

The results obtained show that changes in mechanical properties depend on: (i) the type of mechanical property; (ii) the duration of freeze-thaw exposure; (iii) the condition under which the specimens are tested, either dry or wet; and (iv) the type of polymeric matrix. In general, the highest strength reductions were observed in flexural and compressive strengths, with minimum property retentions of respectively 71% (UP laminate) and 88% (VE laminate); the remaining properties typically showed reductions lower than 10% and, in some cases, they even increased compared to the unaged condition, which was attributed to post-curing mechanisms or the inherent experimental uncertainty. For all mechanical properties, dry specimens showed strength retentions above 90%, revealing the reversibility of the plasticization-induced degradation upon drying, especially in terms of flexural and compressive strengths. For most properties and conditions of testing, the UP laminates presented higher degradation than the VE counterparts, which was expected and is consistent with the DMA test results.

So far, the overall degradation levels observed in this study are comparable (or, at least, have the same order of magnitude) to those reported in other studies available in the literature on the effects of FTC on pultruded GFRP laminates (e.g., Gomez and Casto 1996, Haramis *et al.* 2000, Aniskevich *et al.* 2012, Grammatikos *et al.* 2016). For some results obtained herein, there are some differences to data reported in the literature (which is also not always consistent) and this should also be related with differences in laminate thickness, type of pre-conditioning, temperature ranges, and number and duration of FTC.

As mentioned, in this ongoing investigation further tests will be conducted, after exposure to additional FTC. The results of these tests, together with the analysis of the microstructure of fractured specimens, will disclose additional information about the durability of vacuum infused composite laminates caused by FTC and the underlying degradation mechanisms.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.